

Instruction Leaflet

The SAFER Wearables Study

A study of the acceptability and performance of wearables for atrial fibrillation screening in older adults.

Summary

Thank you for participating in the study. You are playing a vital role in research that aims to prevent strokes in the future.

This leaflet guides you through the study, with instructions for each day. Please read through the leaflet. Call us using the number below when you are ready to start wearing the devices. If we do not hear from you then we will call you in the next few days.

Contact Us

If you have any questions please contact the research team:

Phone: contact us using the following number during working hours (Monday to Friday 9am – 5pm): **01223 331 063**. If we miss your call or if you call outside these hours, there is an answer phone on this number. If you leave a message we will respond to you at the earliest opportunity.

Email: safer-wearables@medschl.cam.ac.uk

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What's included

You should have received:

Wristband

Watch

Chest sensor

Questionnaire
(in envelope)

Plug

Charging cable

Chest dots
(in envelope)

Phone
(optional)

Keep the box, as you'll use it to send the devices back to us.

What to do each day

Day 1 _____	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Read through these instructions • The research team will call you to ask a few questions and explain how to use the devices • Attach the devices • Take watch recordings four times during the day • (if you received a phone) Turn on and plug in the phone
Day 2 _____	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Take watch recordings four times during the day • Continue wearing the devices, checking for any problems • (If you received a phone) Charge the wristband
Day 3 _____	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Take watch recordings four times during the day • Continue wearing the devices, checking for any problems • The research team will call you to help with any problems • (If you received a phone) Charge the wristband
Day 4 _____	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Change the chest dots • Take watch recordings four times during the day • Continue wearing the devices, checking for any problems • (If you received a phone) Charge the wristband
Day 5 _____	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Take watch recordings four times during the day • Continue wearing the devices, checking for any problems • (If you received a phone) Charge the wristband
Day 6 _____	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Take watch recordings four times during the day • Continue wearing the devices, checking for any problems • (If you received a phone) Charge the wristband
Day 7 _____	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Take watch recordings four times during the day • Continue wearing the devices, checking for any problems • (If you received a phone) Charge the wristband
Day 8 _____	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Remove the devices and replace in the packaging • Complete the questionnaire and replace in the packaging • (if received phone) Put phone and charger in packaging • The research team will call you to arrange postage

If you have any questions call the research team on **01223 331 063**.

Day 1

1. The research team will call you

The research team will call, or if you prefer you can call us on **01223 331 063**.

We will ask a few questions about your health.

We will then explain how to attach and use the devices, following the instructions provided below.

2. Attach the wristband and turn it on

Attach the wristband to one wrist (either wrist), making sure it is not loose.

You can press the end of the strap into one of the holes to keep it out of the way.

Turn on the wristband by pressing the button for 2 seconds and then letting go. The screen will light up showing that it is on.

The screen will then go blank – this is normal.

Day 1 *continued*

3. Turn on the watch

Insert the USB end of the charging cable into the plug (see left).

Plug the mains plug into a socket, and turn on the socket.

(see left) Lift the clear plastic flap covering the black square piece, and place the watch on the black square piece, ensuring that it is aligned correctly.

When correctly placed (see right), the watch will light up to indicate that it is turned on. Remove the watch from the square piece.

The plug and cable are no longer required, and can be returned to the packaging.

4. Attach the watch

Attach the watch to your wrist, one finger width from the wrist bone.

You can tuck the strap into the loop to keep it out the way.

Day 1 *continued*

5. Take a watch recording

The watch can record the electrical waves from your heart for 30 seconds at a time – enough time to recognise an irregular heart beat. Follow these steps to take a recording:

1. Sit down comfortably whilst wearing the watch.

2. Place the palm of your opposite hand on the silver panels. The watch will vibrate.

3. Keep your hand there for 30 seconds until the watch vibrates again.

4. Remove your hand after 30 seconds.

Please turn over

Day 1 *continued*

6. Get the chest sensor ready

Do not wear the chest sensor if you have a pacemaker.

You will need:

Chest sensor

2 Chest dots

7. Prepare the chest sensor

i. Turn on the chest sensor by pressing the power button in the middle of the sensor. The sensor will beep and a green light will flash.

Power
button

ii. Attach a chest dot to the press stud at the end of the cable.

Please turn over

Day 1 *continued*

8. Attach the chest sensor

To attach the chest sensor:

- i. Identify the two places where it will attach. Remove any excess hair from these areas by shaving. Make sure the skin is dry.
- ii. Take another chest dot, peel off the paper backing to reveal a sticky surface, and stick on immediately below the collar bone:

- iii. Using the press stud on the back of the chest sensor, press the chest sensor on to the chest dot.
- iv. Stick the second chest dot on to the chest, vertically below the sensor.

9. *(if you received a phone)* Plug in the phone and turn on

Put the phone on charge using the mains charger provided.

Turn it on by pressing the button at the side.

Every Day

1. Take watch recordings

The watch will vibrate to prompt you to take a recording four times a day. Also, take a recording if you feel: breathlessness, light-headed, or heart palpitations (pounding or fluttering).

2. *(on Day 4)* Replace the chest dots

Replace the chest dots on the fourth day, and at any time if they are not sticking well to the chest:

- Un-button the chest sensor
- Pull the old chest dots off.
- Put new chest dots on
- Button the chest sensor on.

3. Continue wearing the devices

- If possible wear the devices the whole time, with the one exception that the wristband is not waterproof, so it should not be submerged in water.
- If the devices feel irritating, check for any signs of skin irritation (such as red or sore skin). If you experience skin irritation then please remove the irritating device and inform the study team: **01223 331 063**
- If you would like a break from wearing any of the devices then do have a break, and re-attach the device when you are ready. Call the study team if you have any questions: **01223 331 063**
- The devices should not be worn in an MRI scanner.

4. *(if you received a phone)* Charge the wristband

- Remove the wristband.
- Remove the screen from the strap.
- Unplug the phone, and use the charger to charge the wristband
- Leave it charging for 1 hour
- Unplug the screen and put it in the strap. Put the phone on charge.
- Check the green lights are lit on the underside of the wristband. If not, press the button to turn it on.
- Attach the wristband to your wrist, making sure it is not too loose.

Day 8

1. Remove the devices and put them in the packaging

- Undo the watch and wristband and put them in the packaging.
- Unbutton the chest-patch from your chest and put it in the packaging.
- (if you received a phone) Unplug the phone and put it in the packaging.

2. Complete the questionnaire

- Please complete the questionnaire. It will take about 15 minutes. Your feedback will help us improve devices for future patients. Thank you.
- Put the questionnaire back in the packaging.

3. Check everything is in the packaging

Wristband

Watch

Chest sensor

Questionnaire

UNIVERSITY OF CAMBRIDGE
Department of Public Health and Primary Care
Participant ID: XXXXX

Questionnaire

The SAFER Wearables Study
A study of the acceptability and performance of wearables for atrial fibrillation screening in older adults.

Instructions
We would be grateful for your feedback on how you found wearing the devices. It will help us understand how to improve them for future patients. It takes about 15 minutes.
Please complete this questionnaire when you finish wearing the devices. Then place it in the packaging with the devices, ready to be sent back to the study team.

Contact Us
If you have any [questions](#) please contact the study team:
Phone: contact us using the following number during working hours (Monday to Friday 9am – 5pm): 01223 331 063. If we miss your call or if you call outside these hours, there is an answer phone on this number. If you leave a [message](#) we will respond to you at the earliest opportunity.
Email: safes-wearables@medsch.cam.ac.uk

Plug

Charging cable

Phone
(optional)

4. Speak to the research team

The research team will call, or if you prefer you can call us on **01223 331 063**. We will arrange a time for the package to be picked up.